

were Konkan Guarav and Phule Pragati. The package of balanced fertilizer use, timely weed control, and intercropping motivated farmers to expand the area under groundnut.

Mango (variety Alphonso) and coconut (variety West Coast tall) have traditionally been grown. Verification trials and on-farm trials on the use of growth inducers and insecticides encouraged farmers to cultivate mango. The use of manure and balanced fertilization for both mango and coconut increased yield and enabled many farmers to grow these in additional areas.

The area under cashew nut increased because of the introduction of varieties such as Vengurle 4 and Vengurle 7, which have bold nut size. The high yield potential of these varieties was observed in the large-scale coppice grafting program established for local cashew trees. As in IVLP activities, the increase in area under horticultural crops was brought about by giving farmers access to facilities under an employment guarantee scheme.

Noteworthy is the number of farmers taking agriculture as a profession—it increased from 497 to 632. Many of them showed interest in cultivating HYVs of rice, mango, cashew nut, and veg-

etables such as chili, particularly the local variety that gets a price premium for its color and taste.

Rice productivity increased from 2.30 t ha⁻¹ (period I) to 4.52 t ha⁻¹ (period II), an increase of 96.5% (Table 2). This increase with respect to the important

Table 2. Increase in productivity of different crops five years after inception of IVLP implementation.

Crop	Period I	Period II	District ^a average
Rice (t ha ⁻¹)	2.30	4.52	1.91
Mango (t ha ⁻¹)	1.59	4.05	2.00
Cashew (t ha ⁻¹)	0.82	0.99	0.91
Coconut (nuts palm ⁻¹)	45,600	96,280	47,000
Vegetable—lady finger (t ha ⁻¹)	6.00	7.30	–

^aNon-IVLP area.

crops such as mango, cashew nut, coconut, and lady's finger was 155%, 20.5%, 11%, and 21.67%, respectively. Compared with the whole Sindhudurga District, which is a non-IVLP area, the increase in productivity of rice, mango, cashew nut, and coconut in Hodawade was 136.6%, 102.5%, 8.8%, and 104.85%, respectively, signifying the impact of TAR-IVLP. Also, between the two periods, the number of pump sets in the village increased by 20.83%, drinking water wells by 54%, cows by 417%, buffaloes by 816%, and poultry by 141%. The increase in number of farm families in the higher, medium, and lower income group was 32,

58, and 45, respectively. The corresponding increase in income was Rs 25,000, Rs 25,000, and Rs 8,000 from period I to period II (Table 3).

Thus, because of the IVLP activities in Hodawade, there was a significant increase in the area under different crops, indicating an increased level of adoption. Similarly, crop productivity improved, leading to favorable changes in the socioeconomic status of the villagers. This is gleaned from the change in asset position of the farmers and the increase in their annual income.

Table 3. Change in number of farm families and their annual income.

Group	Period I	Period II	Difference (no.)
	Number of farm families		
	Annual income (Rs)		
Higher income	12	44	+32
	125,000	150,000	+25,000
Medium income	180	238	+58
	30,000	55,000	+25,000
Lower income	305	350	+45
	10,000	18,000	+8,000
Landless	34	34	0
	6,000	9,000	+3,000

A preliminary forecast of the intensification of global and regional rice production

Wenjun Zhang and Yanhong Qi, Research Institute of Entomology, Zhongshan University, Guangzhou 510275, People's Republic of China E-mail: zhangwenjun@scientist.com

Rice is the staple food that feeds nearly half of the world population (Way and Heong 1994). In the past 3 decades, the steadily increasing rice production has

reduced the food shortage in Asia and the world (IRRI 2003). However, the increased use of land and pesticides aggravates the deterioration of environmental quality

and human health (Altieri 1994, Heong and Escalada 1998, Tilman et al 2001). A perspective on future rice production is essential for estimating the biological and

environmental impacts caused by intensive rice production and for taking appropriate measures to avoid these side effects without threatening overall food security. In this paper, seven variables related to intensive rice production were fitted with data in the past 3 decades and a forecast for the years 2005-25 was made.

The historical data for this forecasting exercise were downloaded from *World rice statistics* (www.irri.org/science/ricesat/index.asp). Seven variables representing rice production, and biological and environmental impacts—e.g., rough rice area (1961-2002), rough rice production (1961-2002), rough rice yield (1961-2002), rice insecticide sales

(1980-96), rice fungicide sales (1980-96), rice herbicide sales (1980-96), and rice pesticide sales (1980-96)—were included for the world, Asia, South America, North and Central America, Africa, Europe, and Oceania (IRRI 2003). Missing data were reasonably interpolated or extrapolated by linear interpolation and linear trend at point (SPSS for Windows 11.0.0, 2001). The temporal trend of each variable was a linear function of time. We thus use univariate linear regression (SPSS for Windows 11.0.0, 2001) to fit and forecast global and regional trends for each of the variables (see table). The adjusted R² of the regression was tested with levels of significance P. The forecast-

ing involved estimates of rice production trajectories of the past 3 decades. These trajectories included impacts of past technological developments, changes in consumer choices, and policy factors. Like other agricultural forecasts, ours assume similar technological, environmental, and behavioral changes in the future (Tilman et al 2001).

Each variable, except for rough rice area of South America, was a linear and strong function of time (see table). With an estimated growth rate of 748,240 ha y⁻¹, the global rough rice area would have an increase of 17.47% by 2025 compared with 2002. Asia ranks first in the growth rate of land use (589,630 ha y⁻¹) and to-

Univariate linear regressions and forecasts for years 2005 and 2025, based on trends observed in the past 3 decades and their time dependence.

		World	Asia	South America	North & Central America	Africa	Europe	Oceania
Forecasts of rough rice area (000 ha)	Annual growth rate	748.24	589.63	17.71	15.68	119.8	7.22	3.36
	Adjusted R ²	0.853**	0.857**	0.020	0.527**	0.964**	0.685**	0.853**
	2005	157,883	140,312	6,417	2,081	8,064	606	178
	2010	161,624	143,260	6,505	2,159	8,663	642	195
	2015	165,366	146,208	6,594	2,237	9,262	678	211
	2020	169,107	149,157	6,682	2,316	9,861	714	228
2025	172,848	152,105	6,771	2,394	10,459	750	245	
Forecasts of rough rice production (000 t)	Annual growth rate	9790.95	8926.58	314.59	188.24	307.31	44.96	31.07
	Adjusted R ²	0.989**	0.987**	0.910**	0.902**	0.915**	0.824**	0.908**
	2005	649,279	593,278	21,001	12,332	17,419	3,215	1,401
	2010	698,234	637,911	22,574	13,273	18,956	3,440	1,557
	2015	747,189	682,544	24,147	14,214	20,492	3,664	1,712
	2020	796,144	727,177	25,719	15,155	22,029	3,889	1,868
2025	845,099	771,809	27,293	16,097	23,566	4,115	2,023	
Forecasts of rough rice yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Annual growth rate	0.055	0.057	0.051	0.072	0.014	0.022	0.091
	Adjusted R ²	0.984**	0.983**	0.805**	0.964**	0.662**	0.310**	0.690**
	2005	4.22	4.26	3.58	6.21	2.26	5.49	8.52
	2010	4.49	4.55	3.84	6.57	2.33	5.59	8.97
	2015	4.77	4.83	4.09	6.93	2.4	5.7	9.43
	2020	5.04	5.12	4.35	7.28	2.47	5.81	9.88
2025	5.32	5.41	4.59	7.64	2.54	5.92	10.34	
Forecasts of rough rice pesticide sales (\$ million)		Insecticide	Fungicide	Herbicide	Pesticide			
	Annual growth rate	47.29	41.43	59.57	163.52			
	Adjusted R ²	0.801**	0.944**	0.949**	0.949**			
	2005	1,818	1,346	1,895	5,306			
	2010	2,054	1,553	2,193	6,124			
	2015	2,291	1,761	2,491	6,942			
2020	2,527	1,968	2,789	7,759				
2025	2,764	2,175	3,086	8,577				

^aLevels of significance: ** = P < 0.0001; * = P < 0.01.

tal area, whereas South America and Africa rank second and third, respectively (see table). Of the six regions, Oceania has the smallest growth rate of land use and total area. If past patterns continue, global rough rice production would increase with an annual rate of 9,790,950 t, largely driven by Asia's growth rate (8,926,580 t y⁻¹) and prevailing production. South America and Africa would share similar annual growth rates and production expectations in rough rice production (see table), while Oceania would hold the least annual growth rate and proportion of rough rice production. With values of 9.88 t ha⁻¹ and 0.091 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹, Oceania has the largest yield expectation and annual growth rate in the six regions, followed by North and Central America. With its predominant proportion in rice production, Asia would yield a similar production forecast in 2025 (5.41 t ha⁻¹) and annual growth rate (0.057 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹) with the world (5.32 t ha⁻¹ and 0.055 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹, respectively). Global annual pesticide sales would continually increase at the annual growth rate of \$163.52 million (see table). The global increase in annual herbicide sales (\$59.57

million y⁻¹) is the fastest compared with sales of insecticide (\$47.29 million y⁻¹) and fungicide (\$41.43 million). By 2025, global rice pesticide sales would reach \$8,577 million.

If past patterns continue, area, production, yield, and pesticides of rough rice for the world, Asia, America, Europe, Africa, and Oceania would increase at constant annual growth rates. Asia is the rice production center in the world and this continent would determine the future trend of global rice production. South America and Africa would remain second and third in production, yield, and annual growth rate of rough rice. Oceania would continue to hold the highest yield in the next 20 years. The global need for rice herbicide was larger than that for insecticide and fungicide and this trend would remain in the future. Habitat destruction and pesticide use in rice production cause environmental degradation or affect human health (Altieri 1994, Heong and Escalada 1998, Tilman et al 2001). Advances in rice science and technology and sound policy decisions are needed to avoid these outcomes.

With advances in technology and in societies, however, these

patterns could change and future intensification of rice production could deviate from what is predicted. Further forecasts may be conducted with more dependent and independent variables taken into consideration.

Acknowledgment

This research was partially supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China, through Grant No. 30170184, and the Foundation of Scientific Research for Personnel from Abroad through the Ministry of Education of China 2000.

References

- Altieri MA. 1994. Biodiversity and pest management in agroecosystems. New York: Haworth Press. 185 p.
- Heong KL, Escalada M. 1998. Pest management of rice farmers in Asia. Manila (Philippines): International Rice Research Institute. 245 p.
- IRRI (International Rice Research Institute). 2003. World rice statistics. Manila (Philippines): IRRI.
- Tilman D, Fargione J, Wolff B. 2001. Forecasting agriculturally driven global environmental change. *Science*: 292:281-284.
- Way MJ, Heong KL. 1994. The role of biodiversity in the dynamics and management of insect pests of tropical irrigated rice—a review. *Bull. Entomol. Res.* 84:567-587.

Farmer participatory learning on integrated crop management of lowland rice in Mali

F.E. Nwilene, Africa Rice Center (WARDA), PMB 5320, Ibadan, Nigeria; M.A. Togola and O. Youm, Africa Rice Center (WARDA), 01 BP 2031, Cotonou, Benin Republic; A. Hamadou, Institute of Rural Economy/Centre Regional de Recherche Agronomique, Sikasso, Mali E-mail: f.nwilene@cgiar.org

The African rice gall midge (AfRGM) *Orseolia oryziivora* Harris and Gagné and rice yellow mottle virus (RYMV) are principal biotic constraints to the sustainable intensification of rainfed

and irrigated lowland rice, posing the most serious challenge to human endeavors in West Africa (Nwilene et al 2002). Considerable progress has been made to control both stresses through

integrated pest management (IPM) components. But, there has been no focus on farmers' needs, knowledge, and capacity for learning ways of managing pest and disease problems under